

Roadmap to open and shared science

A lever for deploying sustainability science and strengthening science-society dialogue

Sustainable development challenges require strong commitments to preserve the future of the planet and its populations, with particularly critical challenges in the regions of the world where IRD has a presence. Launched more than 20 years ago, the international open science movement offers us the opportunity to support more ethical, shared and accessible research in pursuit of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Open science is not an end in itself but one of the levers we have to promote and deploy sustainability science among scientific communities in the Global South.

The most common policies and models of access to publications, data, source code and protocols constitute a serious obstacle to the dissemination of knowledge and know-how, especially to the Global South. Open access to them, and in general to our results research, in digital format is a decisive means of breaking down disciplinary silos and linking different research efforts. It is a necessity for conducting interdisciplinary projects more effectively and for strengthening collaborative approaches. Making our products easily findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable is an essential prerequisite for the advancement of scientific knowledge and its reuse by research communities and socio-economic actors. It is thus a factor of innovation in the South, provided that the conditions of appropriation are met and that a science-society dialogue approach complements the opening up of research results.

An opportunity to transform our research practices

These issues are now at the heart of national, European and international scientific strategies. Over the last decade, we have gone from incentivising policies to injunctions to open up research. 'As open as possible, as closed as necessary' is the new doctrine. IRD, which has already been disseminating its publications in open access form for 30 years thanks to the pioneering efforts of its IST department, has taken advantage of these incentives and regulatory frameworks to expand the culture of open access, ranging from scientific publications to open data.

The 2019-2023 Digital Master Plan already incorporates certain technical building blocks essential to the opening up of our products (Horizon open archive and DataSuds data repository) and has plans for others (software forge, electronic laboratory notebooks). Furthermore, IRD has recently adopted a Charter for deriving value from and sharing and dissemination of research results, which promotes a model of equitable scientific partnership based on the co-construction of research programmes, conventions, methods and practices.

Nevertheless, these efforts need to be bolstered and better coordinated in order to become a sustainable part of IRD's activities. They must also be widened to encourage the sharing of research with other actors of society. Our goal must be a sustainable transformation of our research practices through the entire life cycles of projects and within our partnership mechanisms.

Adoption of this roadmap will provide IRD with the means to fulfil its ambitions for a science that is more open and better shared with society. It also allows us to set the major themes and objectives that IRD will pursue with its partners in the Global South, as well as with its academic partners in the Global North, with whom the IRD will commit to coordinating and pooling its efforts.

The creation of the Mission for Open Science (French: MSO) within the Science division will ensure the operational implementation of the roadmap, which is transverse in nature, mainly in synergy with MCST, DDUNI and DMOB. It will be carried out in coherence with the five other objectives of IRD's scientific trajectory and more particularly with those pertaining to the deployment of sustainability science and the environmental roadmap.

Theme 1 – Opening up and dissemination of data, publications, software and protocols

Overall objective: Opening up and dissemination of data, publications, software and protocols generated from research at IRD

The opening up of research results in all their forms must be done in partnership with and for the benefit of all, scientists, economic actors and civil society.

Objective 1: Developing a digital production ecosystem at IRD

The IRD's productions, in conjunction with national and European services, must be made FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable): publications (strengthening the links between Horizon and HAL/OpenAire), data (DataSuds and national data service), software and code (IRD software forge, Software Heritage), protocols (electronic laboratory notebooks). To this end, scientists must be supported in the FAIRisation of their research results. In this way, the deployment of tools dedicated to the collaborative use of these FAIR data will be facilitated and will allow IRD to respond better to the major SDG challenges, in line with its institutional strategy.

Objective 2: Supporting scientists in the implementation of open science at IRD

IRD is committed to formalising service offers dedicated to FAIRisation in order to support each scientist, each discipline, in its data dissemination, value derivation and opening up strategy. These service offers must cover all digital productions – publications, data and data management plans, software, protocols – via an optimisation of procedures in a context of limited human resources.

Objective 3: Strengthening data skills and professions at IRD

Data management professionals are present in one form or another in all IRD research units, but are often under-utilised and insufficient in number to meet the institute's major scientific challenges. They must therefore be strengthened through appropriate training, new targeted recruitment and the networking of skills.

Objective 4: Supporting new forms of open and quality publications as part of a virtuous model

IRD is committed to promoting new modes of publication that follow the diamond model (free for authors and readers), or that promote bibliodiversity, such as those recommended by *Peer Community In*. In addition, IRD should consider launching a journal dedicated to sustainability science and based on these models. Finally, it is important to raise awareness of alternative publishing models and bibliodiversity among our partners in the Global South.

Theme 2 – Cooperation on open science with countries of the Global South

Main objective: Developing open science with countries of the Global South

IRD must be both an actor and a facilitator in the implementation of open science in the Global South. It has to perform these roles while respecting its partners and while being conscious of their constraints and the specific context of each project and each partnership. To this end, IRD has adopted an approach that aims to raise awareness among the scientific community in the Global South, to negotiate the modalities for integrating open science, to build capacity and, finally, to contribute to the development of data infrastructure in this part of the world.

Objective 1: Raising awareness of open science among IRD partners

IRD has to raise awareness among its partners in the Global South about the challenges, benefits and risks of open science through workshops, explanatory guides and webinars. The priority target audience should be those involved in IRD's partnership mechanisms.

Objective 2: Building the modalities of open science with partners

Open science must be adapted to the needs of partners in the Global South while taking their constraints and expectations into account. It is also a matter of involving them in the stages of dissemination, sharing and utilisation of data by applying our principles of deriving value from and sharing of research results. For example, IRD is committed to ensuring prior consent from partners before opening up co-produced data.

Objective 3: Building data management capacity in the Global South

IRD must deploy an open science pedagogy by co-designing undergraduate and graduate courses with universities in the Global South. Training in open science must be combined with capacity building in data management to avoid a skills gap. This training must focus on methodologies and tools for managing and deriving value from data. IRD offers its partners continuing education modules for operational knowledge of open science tools and practices.

Objective 4: Helping develop and strengthen data infrastructure in the Global South

Access to digital infrastructure (network, storage and computing) is a prerequisite for open science. Thanks to its expertise, its support to African digital infrastructure projects (Wacren, NREN, etc.), and its involvement in international initiatives (GBIF, RDA, etc.), IRD is committed to contributing to and strengthening data services and their scientific use. It must leverage its presence on the European scene (EOSC programme) to facilitate access to European digital infrastructure for partners in the Global South. Its participation in projects with its own funds is also a lever for promoting open science.

Objective 5: Supporting the contribution of partners from the Global South on the international scene

The presence and influence of countries of the Global South in organisations that are working on open science is essential to ensure that their issues and points of view gain recognition. IRD is committed to supporting its partners in the Global South so that they integrate regional or international reflections (COAR, RDA, etc.) in order to better promote an open science culture adapted to their contexts. IRD must help partners network by organising events, involving the network of representatives and relying on the French scientific cooperation network in the countries or regions of intervention.

Theme 3 – Opening up of science to society

Main objective: Promoting the sharing of research with all actors in society

Science must be open to all socio-economic actors, in an ethical manner and at all stages of knowledge production. IRD is committed to undertaking its research in dialogue with society, from its planning and during its implementation, in order to contribute to economic and social innovations in the framework of an equitable partnership.

Objective 1: Building up IRD’s capacity to conduct science-society dialogues and to share research results

IRD scientists and its other staff should be trained in knowledge transfer and in conducting science-society dialogues, and mediators should be mobilised to facilitate this dialogue. These actions can be conducted with partner institutions.

Objective 2: Supporting the deployment of open science with its beneficiaries to improve its impact

Engaging society in the research process helps to ensure that new research knowledge leads to solutions that are better accepted and which contribute to sustainable development. Therefore, IRD must involve the final beneficiaries in the process of planning and undertaking research in order to increase its attractiveness and societal usefulness for the communities concerned.

Objective 3: Making results of research on priority societal issues more appropriable

Research results can help society’s actors better understand the potential implications of the decisions they take and to better respond to the challenges that confront them. Thus, for the major challenges linked to the SDGs (One Health, climate change, migration, etc.), IRD must make a specific effort to ensure that the results of its research are accessible to and appropriated by as many people as possible, via web portals, educational activities and dedicated resources. Multilingualism will be emphasised in order to overcome the language barrier and reach local communities.

Theme 4 – Training and acculturation

Main objective: Developing an open science culture and open science skills within the IRD world
Developing open science requires the acculturation and training of all in the IRD world, i.e., the institute's agents, its joint research units and its institutional instruments. To this end, they will have access to numerous educational resources on IRD's e-learning platform.

Objective 1: Familiarising all with open science, its challenges and benefits

To begin with, it is important that everyone in the IRD world understands the main principles of open science, its challenges and its benefits. For each category of target audience (such as newcomers), it is necessary to make available adapted presentations and dedicated resources. The aim is to dismantle prejudices about open science, get as many people on board as possible and motivate changes in practices.

Objective 2: Training in good open science practices concerning data, publications, software, protocols

Although training already exists, both within and outside IRD, it is needed on both why and how to do open science. This includes discovering the tools and methods for data FAIRisation, opening up of code and protocols, and making publications available in open access. All teaching modalities should be considered: traditional courses, practical workshops, in-person education or e-learning.

Objective 3: Opening up the training materials and educational resources produced by IRD

Open science principles can be extended to IRD's educational materials and resources, across all scientific fields, which should be released as 'Open Educational Resources (OER)' under a licence that allows the five Rs: retain, reuse, revise, remix, redistribute. Educational content created by IRD and its members should be made available under an open source license whenever possible.

Theme 5 – Open science in IRD’s institutional framework

Main objective: Making open science a part of IRD’s institutional framework

Open science is not a fad but a new paradigm. It requires new skills that IRD must acquire and new practices it must deploy on a long-term basis, across all disciplines. This requires defining principles and formulating concrete prescriptions for their implementation, proposing levers to support changes in practices, and being present on the national and international stage to influence policies and funding allocations (financial and human resources).

Objective 1: Establishing the principles and guidelines of open science at IRD

In order to ensure environmental sustainability and the sovereignty of the digital objects produced, it is necessary to define the general framework and concrete prescriptions for open science at IRD. These must include a strategy for publishing and depositing data and source code via open archives and repositories (Horizon for publications, DataSuds for data). In addition, IRD must look after the Global South’s interests in the context of subscription negotiations with publishers or of the transition to open access.

Objective 2: Raising awareness of IRD’s commitment and unique approach to open science

As a prerequisite to its strategy of influence and in order to be recognised as a major open science actor in the Global South, IRD must raise awareness through its institutional statements of its commitment to and uniqueness in the implementation of open science.

Objective 3: Integrating open science into IRD’s strategy of influence

In all its actions of influence and scientific diplomacy, IRD is committed, along with its donors, to transmit the message of open and shared science. In the European Union and in the countries in which it has a presence, in the international bodies that set the rules and standards of research in partnership, IRD must put forth its vision and defend the objectives presented in this roadmap. In this way, open science will become a strong marker of IRD’s strategy of influence.

Objective 4: Adopting an operational framework and providing resources to meet the goals of this roadmap

In synergy with its academic partners in the Global North and the Global South, and with the pooling of resources whenever possible, IRD is committed to developing a multi-annual strategy to provide resources to meet the goals of this roadmap. The implementation of the open science policy within the institute is led by its Science division, which ensures multidisciplinary and transversal coordination, and which also relies on the Support and Development units.

Objective 5: Taking open science into account in the processes to evaluate IRD scientists and systems

Research practices will not change unless adherence to open science principles is made a criterion for evaluating the quality of research activity. New modalities of individual evaluation must be discussed with the internal consultation and evaluation bodies, so that efforts in favour of open dissemination of productions and of science-society dialogues are recognised. Finally, IRD must make open science one of the major evaluation criteria in its partnership mechanisms.

Objective 6: Evaluating the implementation of the roadmap for open and shared science

IRD must develop a set of qualitative and quantitative indicators to assess its trajectory of the opening up of its scientific productions. These indicators should be defined and implemented in a manner that they can be integrated into IRD's governance dashboard and contribute to the open science barometer at the national level. Moreover, the monitoring of the roadmap's implementation will involve IRD's partners in the Global South. This regular monitoring will be presented to IRD's governing body.

Some key figures

On current practices

- **80% of publications written** by IRD scientists are open access
- Nearly **200 books** published by Éditions de l'IRD (IRD's internal publications unit) are **open access** on the OpenEditions Books platform
- **103 datasets** have been **deposited** in the DataSuds data repository since September 2019

On the services currently deployed

- Horizon Plein Textes: created in 1996, hosts **104,000 scientific publications** of all types, **70%** of which are **open access**; these documents are downloaded more than 8000 times a day, with almost 70% of the downloads being from countries in the Global South
- DataSuds: created in 2019, **4000 uploaded files** stored in 103 datasets; **5000 total downloads**
- In 2019, more than **200 hours of training in conducting research** and information management, including training in open science (publishing in *Open Access*, learning about *Open Access* resources, research data, etc.), especially for doctoral students and partners in the Global South.

IRD structures involved in the implementation of open science

In yellow: contributions
In red: departments and services

Figure text:

Derivation of economic value
Derivation of societal value
Raising awareness and training
Open Science tools
Communications
Strategy and means
Governance
Law and rights